

Building Resilient Mechanisms for Joint Socio-Economic Activities: Insights from Institutional Design Principles

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Abstract: This paper explores the application of the "Institutional Analysis and Development" (IAD) framework, pioneered by Elinor Ostrom, to develop an abstract model for mechanisms facilitating joint socio-economic activities. By generalizing IAD's principles of institutional design, the study describes the structure and key functions of an abstract mechanism for joint activity and identifies a set of building blocks enabling the creation of real-world mechanisms such as networks, hierarchies, markets, and institutions. These mechanisms are analyzed through the lens of communication modes—direct, indirect, and absent—highlighting their role in coordination and governance. The research conceptualizes mechanism design as an optimization task. The construction of joint activity mechanisms is viewed as a task of selecting the optimal combination of building blocks to suit the specific characteristics of the joint activity and its surrounding environment. The prospects for developing a formal model of joint activity mechanisms are also discussed. The study introduces the notion of a "metamechanism" to guide the evolution and hybridization of the traditional mechanisms. This approach enhances understanding of how diverse mechanisms emerge and adapt to socio-economic complexities, providing a theoretical basis for improving collective action systems. The findings have broad implications for the study of governance, organizational design, and the management of commons.

Keywords: principles of institutional design, joint activity, abstract mechanism, network, hierarchy, market, institution

JEL: B41, D02, D7, D82, D83, D9

1. Introduction

The "Institutional Analysis and Development" (IAD) framework (Ostrom, 2005; Lara, 2015), co-authored by Nobel laureate in economics Elinor Ostrom, is based on empirical analyses of the creation, use, and improvement of institutional structures in different countries. One of the fundamental outcomes of this research is the identification of universal building blocks for creating institutions, along with the development of design principles for building sustainable institutions. This study focuses on the institutional design principles developed within the IAD framework (Ostrom, 2005, p. 259). These principles consist of eight key points, some of which include sub-points (Ostrom, 2010, p. 653).

The proposed study explores the hypothesis that these design principles describe concepts common to different mechanisms regulating joint socio-economic activities. These common concepts are conceptualized in this study as an abstract mechanism of joint activity, designed to create conditions for the sustainable generation of benefits for participants in an environment characterized by unpredictable disturbances. Thus, all hypothetical and observed mechanisms analyzed in this study are considered as implementations of this abstract mechanism in various types of joint activity and contexts.

A generalization of the IAD design principles provides a set of requirements for the abstract mechanism:

1. Fulfillment of necessary initial conditions related to both the joint activity and its participants.
2. The presence of a method of coordination that optimally accounts for the capabilities and intentions of participants.
3. The presence of a governance method that ensures the resilience of joint activity under conditions of random changes.
4. Integration of the mechanism into an existing system of joint activity mechanisms and participant relationships.

Requirements 1 and 4 emphasize the need for synchronization within the mechanism and across the broader socio-economic system. The structure and key functions of the mechanism itself are determined by the methods of coordination and governance (requirements 2 and 3), which align with ideas presented in studies by Ostrom and her colleagues.

Among the many factors influencing the practical implementation of the abstract mechanism, the process of information exchange between participants in joint activities plays a crucial role. These processes are largely determined by the modes of communication among participants. The study identifies three primary modes of communication:

- a. Direct communication.
- b. Indirect communication.
- c. Absence of communication.

These modes encompass all possible forms of communication among participants.

Incorporating communication modes into the abstract mechanism description allows for the consideration of different implementation options for joint activity mechanisms. The resulting implementations of the mechanism's functions under the three communication modes form the initial set of "building blocks" that can be used to create real mechanisms for joint activities. This set can be expanded by exploring additional aspects of the mechanism's functions. Such approach can be seen as a response to the challenge that Ostrom described as the need to identify universal building blocks that will allow one to describe the mechanisms of joint activity in markets, hierarchies, families, sports, legislatures, etc. (Ostrom, 2009, p. 5).

Using this set of building blocks, the study describes real mechanisms of the "network," "hierarchy," "market," and "institution" types. The analysis reveals that a "network" mechanism represents an implementation of the abstract mechanism using direct communication, where coordination is achieved through negotiation among participants. The "hierarchy" mechanism is derived from the "network" mechanism, with participants delegating the right to determine the content of their activities to managers. The "market" mechanism represents an implementation of the abstract mechanism using indirect communication, where coordination occurs through trial and error, a process referred to as "Walrasian tâtonnement" in the literature (Hurwicz & Reiter, 2006). The "institution" mechanism represents the use of the abstract mechanism in the absence of current communication, where coordination relies on shared rules and norms established during prior communications.

This approach frames the construction of mechanisms for joint activities as an optimization problem: selecting building blocks that maximize the mechanism's efficiency, defined as the

ratio of benefits from joint activity to costs related with the mechanism. The characteristics of the joint activity and its environment establish the constraints for this optimization. The choice of a specific method or model framework for formalizing the general model of the joint activity mechanism and its optimization technique is beyond the scope of this study. Additional opportunities to enhance mechanism efficiency may arise by modifying the socio-economic system's structural components. To address these possibilities, the study introduces the concept of a "metamechanism," which governs the processes involved in constructing joint activity mechanisms.

The results of this study contribute to the methodological foundation for describing the patterns that lead to the formation of hybrid mechanisms and studying principles for constructing effective mechanisms for various types of joint socio-economic activities.

Section 2 examines the structure and functions of the abstract mechanism for joint activity, based on generalized IAD design principles, which are presented in Appendix 1. Section 3 focuses on forming the initial set of building blocks by describing the implementation of the abstract mechanism's functions in three communication modes. Appendix 2 provides a detailed description of 18 building blocks. Using these building blocks, descriptions and analyses of mechanisms of the "network," "hierarchy," "market," and "institution" types are presented. Appendix 3 includes a case study based on an example from the IAD framework. Section 4 addresses the problem of modeling mechanisms for joint activity. Finally, the conclusion outlines research questions for future exploration.

2. Abstract Mechanism Based on the Principles of Institutional Design

To suit the study aims it is necessary to clarify and generalize certain concepts used in the IAD framework .

2.1. Generalization of Key IAD Concepts

The IAD framework introduces several novel concepts to describe the components of institutions and explain human behavior in various situations (Ostrom, 2005). Some concepts relevant to this study are outlined as follows:

- Individuals engage in a variety of action situations, defined as "the social space where participants with diverse preferences interact, exchange goods and services, solve problems, dominate one another, or fight" (Ostrom, 2005, p. 14). The IAD framework identifies seven groups of variables that form the structure of an action situation, which are universal and minimally necessary for constructing formal models of decision-making in joint activities (ibid).
- To formalize decision-making in action situations, individuals create or use pre-existing institutions, which the IAD framework recommends designing based on eight principles (Ostrom, 2010, p. 653). Institutions are understood as sets of "rules-in-use" adopted by individuals in the form of norms, agreements, and formal rules to structure social interactions and guide collective action (Ostrom, 1990; 2005).
- Action arenas encompass individuals, action situations, various external resources and conditions, and the institutions regulating individual behavior in these situations. An action arena is the environment where all these elements interact and outcomes are produced (Ostrom, 2005, p. 13). Action arenas can exist in diverse contexts, such as households, neighborhoods, local or international councils, firms, and markets (ibid).

The types of activities that emerge from applying the principles of institutional design can be clarified as follows:

- a) Institutional construction activity: developing institutions using design principles.
- b) Institutional application activity: utilizing institutions to regulate the core activity.
- c) Core activity: generating benefits for participants within action situations regulated by institutions.

Thus, activity type (a) creates mechanisms, while type (b) applies these mechanisms to support activity type (c). Ostrom identifies similar structures, where constitutional situations (activity type “a”) define rules-in-use for collective-choice situations (type “b”), which, in turn, determine the rules for operational situations (type “c”) (Ostrom, 2005, pp. 58–59).

For the purposes of this study, joint socio-economic activity is broadly defined as the actions of individuals who expect to gain mutual benefits by working together. According to this definition, all three types of activity “a”-“c” can be classified as joint activities. In the context of this study, we focus solely on core activities (type “c”) as joint activities.

A notable example is the use of common-pool resources, such as fishermen sharing a water basin with limited fish stocks. Here, individuals are compelled to engage in joint activity because they cannot exclude others from accessing the resource, yet their actions affect its availability for everyone. Appendix 3 examines this scenario, where joint activity arises from mutual dependency.

To generalize the above IAD concepts for studying mechanisms like “network,” “hierarchy,” “market,” and “institution,” we define the key concepts:

1. Individuals engaging in joint activities.
2. To make decisions on the content of joint activity that will bring individuals the expected benefit, they create new or use already created mechanisms of joint activity. IAD design principles allow us to describe the structure and functions of a certain abstract mechanism of joint activity, special cases of the implementation of which are mechanisms of the "network", "hierarchy", "market" and "institution" types.
3. The individuals, their joint activities, and corresponding mechanisms, form a socio-economic system. The interconnectedness between the system components exists because all activities and mechanisms in a certain sense "compete" with each other for the limited resources (at least, the time and effort spent) of individuals. Individuals allocate their limited resources among joint activities according to their perception of the required contribution of each activity to the expected total benefit.

The main objects of this study are the structure and functions of the abstract mechanism of joint activity (item 2 in the list above). To simplify the study, we do not consider in detail the issues of describing the properties of individuals and the structure of joint activity (item 1), a good basis for which is the structure of the action situations proposed in IAD. We also do not consider the issues of the functioning of the entire system (item 3), which IAD defines as an arena of actions.

2.2. Abstract Mechanism of Joint Activity

A generalization of IAD design principles (see Appendix 1) reveals the following requirements for an abstract mechanism of joint activity:

1. **Necessary Conditions:** For joint activity to occur, participants must have access to resources with specific characteristics (design principle 1) and a shared understanding of the activity's content (principle 2). Additionally, participants must be able to exchange information and optimize the activity content for maximum benefit. This corresponds to the first structural element of the abstract mechanism, which ensures the necessary conditions for operation.
2. **Coordination Methods:** Participants require methods to account for each other's capabilities, intentions, and actions during decision-making. According to IAD design principle 3, mechanisms of collective choice should be adaptable. This structural element provides following functions:
 - **Accounting:** Considering participants' individual capabilities, intentions and current activities.
 - **Choosing:** Selecting optimal joint activity options based on expected benefits and costs.
 - **Coordinating:** Agreeing on the chosen option to align individual activities.
3. **Governance Methods:** In the most general form, the task of the "governance method" is to maintain the joint activity in the sustainability against the flow of disturbances (IAD design principles 4–6). This structural element provides following functions:
 - **Responsibility:** Fixing responsibilities and implementing joint activities.
 - **Monitoring:** Monitoring implementation, tracking disturbances in the conditions for implementing joint activities.
 - **Sustainability:** Adapting activities and/or mechanisms to maintain the sustainability of benefiting from joint activity in following main ways:
 - elimination of sources of disturbances, if possible (for example, exclusion of certain participants from joint activities);
 - if elimination of disturbances is impossible, then re-coordination of the core activity is performed for the changed conditions;
 - if re-coordination does not produce the required result, then a change in the mechanism itself is performed to adapt it to the changes that have occurred.
4. **System Integration:** The mechanism must align with existing relationships of individuals, labor divisions, and other related mechanisms (principles 7 and 8). This structural element ensures integration into the broader socio-economic system.

For simplicity, this study examines the coordination and governance elements (points 2 and 3) of the abstract mechanism, excluding the emergence (point 1) and integration (point 4) elements. The proposed abstract mechanism enables participants to conduct sustainable and coordinated joint activities, ensuring mutual benefits while addressing potential disturbances.

3. Building Blocks of Joint Activity Mechanisms

The methods of coordination and governance, which form the functional foundation of the mechanism, naturally depend on the characteristics of the process of information exchange between participants in joint activities. Ostrom notes that the type of communication is typically assumed to be present in the action situation (Ostrom, 2005, p. 52). To clarify how communication is integrated into joint activities, we assume that the information exchange process is defined by specific modes of communication between participants. In this study, these communication modes are categorized as direct communications, indirect communications, and the absence of communications.

Incorporating these three communication modes into the description of the abstract mechanism allows us to define the initial set of building blocks for the mechanism. This set consists of various implementations of the mechanism's functions across all these communication modes. It is referred to as "initial" because it can be expanded with additional building blocks that detail other possible implementations of the abstract mechanism's functionality, such as methods for analyzing information, choosing optimal activities, making collective decisions, etc.

3.1. Communication Modes

Based on general concepts regarding individuals and their shared activity environments, we propose that the following primary communication modes exist between agents:

1. **Direct Communications:** This mode involves "face-to-face" interaction among participants in an "all-to-all" manner. It allows for intensive information exchange, negotiations, and mutual agreements among participants.
2. **Indirect Communications:** This mode is mediated through changes in the shared environment. Participants modify the environment (e.g., leaving signals or labels) and observe these changes to gain information about other participants. Decisions about individual activities are then made based on this information. Coordination is achieved through a trial-and-error process. A prominent example of indirect communication is market activity, where a consumer purchasing a product indirectly communicates preferences, which are reflected in pricing and market adjustments.
3. **No Communication:** In this mode, participants rely on pre-established common rules, norms of behavior, cultural backgrounds, or shared experiences created during prior direct or indirect communications. Coordination emerges from participants independently choosing their activities based on these common rules, assuming that others are making decisions similarly. While no real-time communication occurs, participants may still exchange information on unrelated matters through direct or indirect means.

3.2. Initial Set of Building Blocks

The methods for implementing the functions of the abstract mechanism are analyzed for each of the main communication modes: direct, indirect, and no communication. This analysis focuses only on the structural elements of the mechanism related to the coordination method and governance method for simplicity.

For each function of the coordination and governance methods, implementation options are detailed in Appendix 2 (Tables 2.1–2.3 and Tables 2.4–2.6, respectively). These options constitute the building blocks (BBs) for constructing mechanisms for joint activities with various characteristics.

Table 1 summarizes the building blocks associated with communication modes. The numbering of each BB in Table 1 corresponds to its number in the respective Appendix 2 tables.

Table 1. Building Blocks of Joint Activity Mechanisms by Communication Mode

Mechanism Functions	Direct Communications	Indirect Communications	No Communications
Coordination Method			

Mechanism Functions	Direct Communications	Indirect Communications	No Communications
Accounting	1.1. Direct information exchange	1.2. Observation	1.3. Rule-based
Choosing	2.1. Negotiations	2.2. Assumption-based	2.3. Rule-based
Coordinating	3.1. Agreements	3.2. Trial and error with feedback from participants	3.3. Trial and error without participant feedback
Governance Method			
Responsibility	4.1. Collective	4.2. Individual with feedback	4.3. Rule-based with feedback from a regulator
Monitoring	5.1. Collective	5.2. Observation and a regulator	5.3. Observation and a regulator
Sustainability	6.1. Collective maintenance	6.2. Individual/regulator maintenance	6.3. Individual/regulator maintenance

A simple way to use BBs for a given joint activity is to implement all the mechanism's functions using a single communication mode that best aligns with the characteristics of the activity and its environment. In such cases, the mechanism's functions are implemented according to one column in Table 1. This configuration is referred to as the canonical version of the mechanism.

However, participants often use multiple communication modes simultaneously. In these cases, BBs are dynamically combined based on complex algorithms, where participants optimize BB selection to maximize the benefits of joint activities while minimizing the mechanism's operational costs. The actual mechanism thus becomes a dynamic combination of BBs and communication modes. This topic requires further research, with some aspects addressed in the subsequent sections.

3.3. Describing Mechanism Types Using Building Blocks

Based on the characteristics of mechanisms of the “network”, “hierarchy”, “market” and “institution” types presented in the literature, we will describe these mechanisms based on the building blocks from the previous section and analyze some properties of the mechanisms using these descriptions.

Network

The main properties of the “network” type mechanism, described by the concepts of “decentralization”, “flexibility”, “cooperation”, “interdependence” (Powell, 1990; Granovetter, 1983; Provan & Kenis, 2008), correspond to the greatest extent to the implementation of an abstract mechanism in direct communications. In this case, the functions of “accounting” and “choosing” within the coordination method are implemented by direct exchange of information (Tab. 1, BB 1.1) and negotiations (BB 2.1), and coordination of activities is achieved through agreements between the participants (BB 3.1). The functions of the governance method are implemented by collective efforts, which can take various forms. At the same time, direct communications with an increase in the number of participants in joint activities lead to a rapid increase in the participants' costs for

coordination and governance. This explains why the "network" type mechanism is usually used in small groups and why direct communication can foster innovation and efficiency in small, flexible groups. Open-source software development provides real-world examples of the network mechanism. E.g., the Linux project relies on direct communication and decentralized collaboration. Open-source software contributors self-organize through platforms like GitHub, negotiating responsibilities and code contributions directly.

Hierarchy

The hierarchy-type mechanism, the main properties of which are described by the concepts of "distribution of tasks and responsibilities", "centralized decision-making", "command system", etc. (Malone and Crowston, 1994; Weigand, et al., 2003), from the point of view of communication modes, most closely corresponds to direct communication. However, in this case, the participants-performers delegated the right to determine the content of their activities to the participants-managers. For the construction of mechanism, this means that the performers have transferred the execution of a certain part of the functions of the "coordination method" to managers. In the process, performers and managers have established certain relationships between themselves, which are regulated on the basis of rules and belong to the "institution" type mechanism. As a result, some of the direct communications between the participants have been replaced by the "without communications" mode. Due to this, the performers are largely excluded from the processes of direct communication, which reduces the costs associated with the mechanism and makes it possible to significantly increase the number of participants in joint activities and increase the benefits due to deepening specialization and developing the division of labor. Thus, the hierarchy type is a derivative of the network-type mechanism, in which the rejection of some of the properties of the network-type mechanism made it possible to increase the total number of participants in joint activities. A real-world example is the Toyota Production System. Hierarchies like Toyota's lean manufacturing system delegate decision-making to specific roles, balancing authority and accountability.

Market

The "market" type mechanism, the main properties of which are described by the concepts of "information asymmetry", "voluntary exchange", "cooperation", "competition", "price regulation", etc. (Powell, 1990; Williamson, 1975), is an implementation of an abstract mechanism through indirect communications. The "accounting" function for the coordination method is carried out by observing changes in the common environment among participants. The "choosing" is performed individually, and the coordination is achieved by trial and error, known in the literature as "Walrasian tâtonnement" (Hurwicz & Reiter, 2006, p. 19). In indirect communications, the governance functions are initially implemented individually by participants. However, in the practical application of the market mechanism, participants delegate some of the governance functions to a specially created centralized regulator, such as the state. In this case, the relations between the regulator and the participants are governed by rules, i.e., using a mechanism of the "institution" type. Additionally, to enhance the efficiency of the trial-and-error method in market operation, certain changes are made to the structure of the common market environment. Indirect communications, in their typical form, are supplemented in the common environment by a "signal" system. For instance, a system that communicates market prices, supply and demand indicators, etc., to participants. Such a signaling system increases the efficiency of the trial-and-error method by reducing the costs of obtaining necessary information in a processable form. Reducing the costs of the

mechanism through such a signal system, in particular, allows for a significant increase in the number of participants in joint activities. Real-world examples include mechanisms like the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), which uses indirect communication (pricing signals) to coordinate actions among participants. Companies make decisions based on market signals, such as carbon credit prices, demonstrating the role of indirect communication and market-based coordination.

Institution

The mechanism of the “institution” type, the main properties of which are characterized by the concepts of “common rules and norms”, “property rights”, “transaction costs”, etc. (Coase, 1998; North, 1995; Williamson, 2000; Ostrom, 2005), is most consistent with the use of an abstract mechanism in the absence of current communications between participants in joint activities. In this case, the coordination functions “accounting” and “choosing” are implemented by participants individually, and the coordination of their activities is achieved through their use of general rules developed and accepted for use in the process of past communications. Coordination under these conditions is achieved by the fact that participants determine the content of their individual activities based on the assumption that other participants determine the content of their activities on the basis of the same rules. The governance functions are implemented at the individual level. It is also possible to transfer some of the functions to a specially created regulator. A mechanism of this type does not incur current communication costs for participants. This allows it to regulate the joint activities of an unlimited number of participants. Real-world examples include community-based natural resource management systems, e.g. as the fishermen fishing in a common body of water example provided in the Appendix 3.

The descriptions above consider the properties of the types of mechanisms that are related only to the modes of communication. The types of mechanisms, as the consideration shows, can have a canonical form, in which all the functions of the mechanism are realized in the same mode of communication. However, in practice, combinations of several modes of communication are used in mechanisms. As a result, they acquire the characteristics of a hybrid (Ménard, 2004).

The characteristic properties of the types of mechanisms considered are largely determined by the properties of the dominant modes of communication between the participants of the joint activity. Thus, the observed diversity of the types of mechanisms can be explained by the differences between the three modes of communication, which is supplemented by modification options of the canonical versions of the mechanisms (for example, the “hierarchy” type as a modification of the canonical “network” type).

4. Discussion

This study considers joint activity mechanisms as one of the fundamental components of the socio-economic system. The entire system encompasses numerous boundedly rational individuals who maintain various relationships with one another. These individuals operate within a shared environment, which influences how they communicate and execute their joint activities. The primary motivation for joint activities is to gain mutual benefits. However, the shared environment is subject to unpredictable changes (disturbances) that occur with a certain regularity, altering the conditions under which individuals derive benefits. Limited resources within the common environment—whether natural or produced by joint activities—

are used, distributed, exchanged, or consumed by individuals to sustain their activities and livelihoods.

Within such a socio-economic system, the primary role of joint activity mechanisms is to maximize participants' benefits under current conditions in a sustainable manner. To achieve this, the mechanism performs coordination functions, which involve determining the specific activity content of each participant by taking into account the abilities, intentions, and ongoing efforts of other participants, as well as other factors critical to the joint activity. The mechanism also performs governance functions, which are essential for maintaining the sustainable flow of benefits in response to disturbances in the environment. In cases where joint activity involves resource exchange, such as in economic activities, the mechanism ensures efficient coordination of resource allocation among participants.

The mechanism operates and fulfills its tasks through the additional efforts of participants, which are distinct from the core activities that generate benefits. It is natural to assume that these additional efforts, aimed at enabling the mechanism to perform its functions, may vary depending on the mode of communication among participants. Communication modes differ in their ability to maximize benefits by accounting for critical factors, the information about which may be distributed among participants. These modes also differ in their ability to sustain benefits over time and in their associated costs. Higher communication intensity and completeness of factor consideration typically lead to higher mechanism's costs.

Participants in joint activities can combine different communication modes simultaneously or sequentially and adjust these combinations dynamically as needed.

This study proposes an approach that views joint activity mechanisms as a set of functions of an abstract mechanism. The abstract mechanism's functions adapt to the specific characteristics of joint activities through various combinations of building blocks (BBs) and communication modes. Mechanism design, in this context, can be described as the process of selecting BBs to implement the required functions. This selection process involves optimizing the trade-off between the cost increment incurred by using certain BBs and the expected increment of benefit and sustainability that these BBs should allow to obtain.

The operational costs associated with joint activity mechanisms can be classified as transaction costs (Coase, 1998; Williamson, 2000). Sustainability, in this context, refers to the total benefit derived over a given time interval. The ratio of costs to benefits determines the mechanism's efficiency for a specific joint activity and its environmental parameters.

Optimizing the combination of BBs involves selecting the most efficient mechanism design for a given joint activity over a specific time frame. The objective of this optimization is to maximize the mechanism's efficiency. The variables to maximize the efficiency are the set of BBs chosen to implement the mechanism's functions. The constraints for this optimization problem are determined by the characteristics of the joint activity and the parameters of the environment. The dynamic nature of this optimization problem is shaped by the regular occurrence of disturbances, time-varying conditions for deriving benefits, and the bounded rationality of participants, who often settle for acceptable rather than optimal solutions (Simon, 1978). This bounded rationality drives participants to continuously seek improvements in the mechanism's efficiency.

To convert this optimization problem into a model for a joint activity mechanism, it is necessary to establish the relationship between the efficiency of individual BBs (and their combinations) and the characteristics of joint activities and environmental parameters, particularly disturbances.

The characteristics of joint activities vary in several dimensions, including the number of participants—ranging from small groups to global economy—and the degree of variability in activity content. For instance, activities in start-ups often involve high variability as participants experiment with new ideas, while bureaucratic organizations operate with stable, predefined procedures. Disturbances in the common environment also differ in intensity and type. For some activities, disturbances may be rare, while others may experience frequent and intense disruptions, necessitating regular re-coordination of activities and adjustments to the mechanism's structure.

Future research should systematically describe how the characteristics of joint activities and disturbances affect the efficiency of BBs. In this study, we observe that different activity characteristics and environmental conditions lead to varying mechanism costs. In simple terms, the mechanism costs can be conceptualized as the volume and/or complexity of information participants must process to define their activity content. An increase in the volume or complexity of information can lead to longer decision-making times. For participants in a joint activity, this time spent is a cost, since it may reduce the amount of time that participants could spend on obtaining benefits from the core activity and, consequently, diminishing possible benefits.

However, higher costs in some cases can also generate higher benefits. For example, a more complete consideration of factors important for joint activities, associated with a higher level of costs, increases the likelihood of obtaining a greater benefit. An increase in the number of participants in joint activities, on the one hand, leads to an increase in the costs of the mechanism, since each participant in the “all with all” communication significantly increases the volume and complexity of information that must be processed by all participants. On the other hand, an increase in the number of participants also increases the likelihood of each participant obtaining a greater benefit due to improved specialization and the development of the labor division between them.

A formal mathematical model of joint activity mechanisms could provide a foundation for identifying optimal mechanism designs under specific conditions. Such a model could enable the development of advanced algorithms for creating dynamic, adaptive, and time-efficient institutions (Ostrom, 2005, p. 271). However, this model must also account for potential mechanism's efficiency gains resulting from changes in other components of the socio-economic system, such as participant relationships, the common environment, and the structure of joint activities.

The efficiency of the mechanism can be increased by modifying the structure of relationships between the participants in the joint activity. For example, the transition from network peer-to-peer to hierarchically organized relationships among participants, which allows not only to prevent a decrease in the efficiency of the mechanism with an increase in the number of participants, but can also lead to an increase in efficiency. In this case, some participants (performers) delegate to other participants (managers) the rights to determine the content of their activities. Such a structure of relationships between participants reduces the total number of information flows that require processing and, accordingly, reduces the costs of

the mechanism. Another example is when hierarchical or network relationships are added to the relationships between participants based on common rules. For example, fishermen, as participants in forced joint activities (see Appendix 3), when fish stocks decrease, can switch to a hierarchical or network structure of relationships between themselves, which allows them to revise the rules and increase the efficiency of the mechanism of their joint activities.

Reducing the costs of the mechanism and thus increasing its efficiency is also possible by modifying the common environment used by the participants in the joint activity. For example, participants using a mechanism based on indirect communications create a market signaling system that reduces their monitoring costs and simplifies by using the market indicators the determination of the content of their activities. Similarly, the efficiency of mechanisms such as an institution, whose participants regulate their joint activities based on rules, can be increased. For the example of fishermen in Appendix 3, modification of the common environment could mean creating a more accurate system for monitoring fish stocks and algorithms for changing the rules for catching fish used by participants.

Modification of the structure of types of joint activity (e.g. as a labor division development) can also be a way to reduce the costs of the mechanism and increase its efficiency. For joint activity, the efficiency of the mechanism of which decreases, for example, due to an increase in the number of participants, it is possible to divide this activity into relatively independent parts. Each part of the joint activity receives its own mechanism with lower costs. To coordinate the outcomes of individual parts of the activity, a higher-level mechanism is required. As a result, a multi-level structure of nested mechanisms is formed in the socio-economic system, which jointly regulate the entire existing system of types of socio-economic activity (Ostrom, 2005, p. 6). In particular, subtypes can be distinguished from the composition of different types of activity, the optimal mechanism for which are institutions.

Efficiency can also be enhanced by advancing BBs implementations through modern computational tools and information processing algorithms.

Since methods for improving the efficiency of mechanisms involve modifying the structure of the components of the socio-economic system itself, it is necessary to assume the existence of a mechanism that regulates this process. Obviously, this mechanism should be higher level than traditional one that regulate the core joint activity. Based on the general assumptions of this study, the operation of such a mechanism is ensured by the corresponding joint activity of individuals. This brings the discussion back to the list of types of activities associated with the mechanism of joint activity, as presented in section 2.1 above. The hypothesis of the existence of a higher-level mechanism requires an addition to the list in section 2.1. This addition is the activity that creates a metamechanism, which regulates the activities of individuals in the development of traditional mechanisms for the core activity, including changes in the structure of the components of the socio-economic system. Literature contains concepts that are closely related to the idea of a metamechanism. In IAR (Ostrom, 2005, p. 56–59), for example, “metaconstitutional situations” are mentioned, in which participants define the rules of the relevant institution. For similar situations, Buchanan (2018, p. 5) proposes the “metacoordination view”, and Parinov (2023c) discusses the concept of the “metacoordination mechanism”.

Thus, the task of determining the optimal design of a traditional mechanism for main joint activity is part of a broader optimization task, which includes determining the structure of the

components of the socio-economic system. The tool for solving this general optimization task is the metamechanism.

As a summary of the discussion in this section, it should be noted that the hypotheses proposed in this study require empirical verification. In particular, it is necessary to verify the hypothesis that the activity of constructing mechanisms for core joint activity and improving their efficiency is, in turn, also joint, and therefore requires the presence of a corresponding metamechanism. It is possible that both the metamechanism and traditional mechanisms are described by a similar theoretical model. Developing ways to improve the efficiency of the metamechanism could significantly reduce the costs individuals face in enhancing the efficiency of the mechanisms for their core activity, which, in practical implementation, may lead to a substantial increase in the efficiency of the socio-economic system as a whole.

5. Conclusion

The proposed approach generalizes and develops the results of the IAR concept concerning the universal building blocks and design principles of resilient institutions. Among the various continuations and developments of the presented study, one could note the possibility of expanding the set of building blocks of an abstract mechanism. Representing mechanisms of different types as building blocks compositions allows for providing the mechanisms with sufficiently strict definitions, including the separation of its canonical versions from modifications and hybrids, what was done in the first approximation in (Parinov, 2023a). The results obtained in this study and a groundwork from (Parinov, 2023b) contribute to the development of methods for studying the principles of designing effective mechanisms for different types of joint socio-economic activities.

As the author sees it, this approach could be useful for the study of governance, organizational design, institutional economics, and the management of commons. In particular, it allows for the investigation of the following questions:

- What factors and patterns determine the mechanism with the best combination of building blocks for a given joint activity? Specifically, what should be the algorithm for creating an optimal "institution" type mechanism?
- For which types of joint activity is a mechanism of a specific type most suitable? For example, what characteristics should joint activity have for the "institution" type mechanism to be the best solution?
- What is the fundamental feature of an "institution" type mechanism? Why is the use of common rules, which define the nature of the "institution" type mechanism, also present in mechanisms of other types such as "network," "hierarchy," and "market"?

Acknowledgments

References

- Coase, R. (1998). "The New Institutional Economics," *American Economic Review*, 88(2), pp. 72–74.
- Granovetter, M. (1983). The strength of weak ties: A network theory revisited. *Sociological theory*, 201-233.

- Hurwicz, L., & Reiter, S. (2006). *Designing economic mechanisms*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lara, A. (2015). Rationality and complexity in the work of Elinor Ostrom. *International Journal of the Commons*, 9(2), 573-594.
- Malone, T. W., & Crowston, K. (1994). The interdisciplinary study of coordination. // *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 26(1), 87-119
- Ménard, C. (2004). The economics of hybrid organizations. *Journal of Institutional and Theoretical Economics* 160 (2004), 1–32.
- North, D. C. (1995). "The New Institutional Economics and Third World Development" in *The New Institutional Economics and Third World Development*, J. Harriss, J. Hunter, and C. M. Lewis, ed., pp. 17–26.
- Ostrom, E. (1990). *Governing the commons: The evolution of institutions for collective action*. Cambridge university press.
- Ostrom E. (2005). *Understanding Institutional Diversity*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Ostrom, E. (2010). Beyond markets and states: polycentric governance of complex economic systems. *American economic review*, 100(3), 641-672.
- Parinov, S. (2023a). Micro-level description of the economic coordination. Preprint at Munich Personal RePEc Archive, https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/114816/1/MPRA_paper_114816.pdf (published as Parinov, S.I. Micro level of economic coordination processes. *Voprosy Ekonomiki*. 2023;(2):127-144. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.32609/0042-8736-2023-2-127-144>)
- Parinov, S. (2023b). Socio-Economic Coordination Mechanisms Design: Conceptual Model. Preprint at Munich Personal RePEc Archive, <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/117282/1/coordination-mechanism-design-en.pdf> (published as Parinov, S.I. Towards economic coordination mechanisms design. *Voprosy Ekonomiki*. 2023;(9):121-137. (In Russ.) <https://doi.org/10.32609/0042-8736-2023-9-121-137>)
- Parinov, S. (2023c). Fundamental socio-economic coordination process and metacoordination. Preprint at Munich Personal RePEc Archive, https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/118980/1/MPRA_paper_118980.pdf
- Powell, W. W. (1990). Neither market nor hierarchy: Network forms of organization. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, v. 12, p., 295-336.
- Provan, K. G., & Kenis, P. (2008). Modes of network governance: Structure, management, and effectiveness. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 18(2), 229-252.
- Simon, H. A. (1978). Rationality as Process and as Product of Thought. Richard T. Ely Lecture // *American Economic Review*, May 1978, v.68, no.2, p.1–16.

Weigand, H., van der Poll, F., & de Moor, A. (2003). Coordination through communication. In Proceedings of the 8th International Working Conference on the Language-Action Perspective on Communication Modelling. Tilburg, The Netherlands.

Williamson, O.E. (1975). Markets and hierarchies: Analysis and antitrust implications. New York: Free Press.

Williamson, O. E. (2000). "The New Institutional Economics: Taking Stock, Looking Ahead," Journal of Economic Literature, 38(3), pp. 595–613

Supplementary materials

Appendix 1: “Generalization of the institutional design principles”

Let us assume that the description of the design principles of IAD contains ideas about the structure and basic functions that are common to all types of joint activity mechanisms. Based on the generalized concepts from Section 2.1, we will select from these descriptions general ideas about the character of activities aimed at constructing sustainable institutions. In fact, this is an attempt to detail the ideas about the activity of type “a” from the list of types in Section 2.1.

The principles consist of eight points (Ostrom, 2010, p. 653). For each principle, there is detailed explanations with examples (Ostrom, 2005, pp. 260–270). Also useful for understanding the essence of the principles are the questions for institutional analysts that Ostrom has formulated for each principle (Ostrom, 2005, p. 271).

The list below provides the design principles (Ostrom, 2005, p. 259) with the author's comments:

1. “*Clearly defined boundaries*. The boundaries of the resource system (e.g., irrigation system or fishery) and the individuals or households with rights to harvest resource units are clearly defined” (Ostrom, 2005, p. 259).

In its most general form, this principle speaks of the need to clearly define all the main parameters of joint activities, including its participants and the resources used.

2. “*Proportional equivalence between benefits and costs*. Rules specifying the amount of resource products that a user is allocated are related to local conditions and to rules requiring labour, materials, and/or money inputs” (ibid.).

The second principle requires assessing the expected benefits of the joint activity and the associated costs, as well as the relationship between the costs and benefits.

These first two principles, in the most general sense, can be interpreted as a requirement for the presence of necessary initial conditions that relate to the content of the joint activity, its participants, as well as to assessments of the costs and benefits of the joint activity for its participants.

3. “*Collective-choice arrangements*. Many of the individuals affected by harvesting and protection rules are included in the group who can modify these rules” (ibid.).

The third design principle, which concerns collective-choice and decision making, can be detailed using Ostrom's model of the individual. The three components of human behavior with making collective-choice and decision making (Ostrom, 2005, p. 103) are:

1. *the way that participants acquire, process, represent, retain, and use information;*
2. *the valuation that participants assign to actions and outcomes; and*
3. *the processes (maximizing, satisficing, or using diverse heuristics) that participants use for selecting particular actions or strategic chains of actions in light of their resources.*

Benefiting from a joint activity implies that its mechanism ensures that the participants take each other's capabilities, intentions, and current activities into account. This is what allows them to receive more benefits from the joint activity than from individual one. Generalizing Ostrom's ideas, the mechanism of joint activity should contain collective-choice procedures that allow participants to mutually take into account each other's capabilities, intentions, and current activities in order to determine the content of their own activity.

Such procedures of the mechanism should include methods for obtaining and processing information on factors important for joint activities, including information that is distributed between participants. Also, in the process of analyzing the information received, the participants should be able to assess the expected benefit from various options for joint activities, as well as the amount of costs associated with this. Based on the assessments received for different options for activities, the participants in one way or another agree on which content of the joint activity is the best. In fact, all these procedures represent a process of coordination of the participants in the joint activity.

4. “*Monitoring*. Monitors, who actively audit biophysical conditions and user behavior, are at least partially accountable to the users and/or are the users themselves” (ibid.).
5. “*Graduated sanctions*. Users who violate rules-in-use are likely to receive graduated sanctions (depending on the seriousness and context of the offense) from other users, from officials accountable to these users, or from both” (ibid.).
6. “*Conflict-resolution mechanisms*. Users and their officials have rapid access to low-cost, local arenas to resolve conflict among users or between users and officials” (ibid.).

The next three design principles create conditions for the sustainable implementation of decisions taken by participants on the content of their joint activities. The need to maintain sustainability is created by random changes (disturbances) in the common environment and in the conditions for joint activities, including the state and actions of the participants themselves.

In the context of this study, one more principle should be explicitly added to this: fixing the responsibility of participants. This means that it is necessary to develop an effective method for fixing the responsibility of participants for the implementation of agreed decisions. Then the set of conditions for the sustainable implementation of joint activities receives logical completeness.

With this addition, the monitoring system gives participants the opportunity to identify and analyze discrepancies between the expected and actual results of joint activities. The presence of responsibility of participants for the implementation of decisions made allows, when analyzing discrepancies, to identify the causes and culprits. Sanctions for violating the rules of joint activities and methods for resolving conflicts increase their sustainability. This set of procedures, in total, implements the process of governance of joint activities.

7. *“Minimal recognition of rights to organize.* The rights of users to devise their own institutions are not challenged by external governmental authorities, and users have long-term tenure rights to the resource” (ibid.).

8. *“Nestled enterprises.* Appropriation, provision, monitoring, enforcement, conflict resolution, and governance activities are organized in multiple layers of nested enterprises” (ibid.).

The last two principles, as applied to joint activities, require the establishment of multi-level relationships with the external environment and/or with the existing system of various types of joint activities. In particular, integration into the socio-economic system is required at the level of participants (principle 7) and at the level of mechanisms and content of joint activities (principle 8). In addition, the external environment should allow participants to determine the content they need both for the activity itself and, in some cases, for the corresponding mechanism.

Appendix 2: Initial set of building blocks of the joint activity mechanisms

For all functions of the "coordination method", as well as the functions of the "governance method", the options for their implementation are outlined below in Tables 2.1-2.3 and Tables 2.4-2.6, respectively. These options serve as building blocks for constructing mechanisms of joint activities of various types and characteristics.

Table 2.1. Building blocks for implementing the function "Accounting" of the "Coordination Method"

Communications	Building blocks
Direct	1.1. Direct exchange of information in an "all to all" manner. Informing participants about capabilities and intentions regarding joint activities.
Indirect	1.2. Leaving labels and traces by all participants in a common environment. Observing changes in the environment, including those created by other participants. Forming assumptions about the capabilities and intentions of other participants regarding joint activities.
Absent	1.3. Forming assumptions about others' potential activities based on the premise that everyone follows predefined rules for the current situation in joint activities.

The building blocks from Table 2.1 differ in participants' abilities to enhance the completeness of mutual consideration of each other's capabilities and intentions to determine the content of their activities. The higher the completeness of consideration, the greater the likelihood of achieving the maximum possible benefit from their joint activities. However, increasing completeness raises the participants' costs for communication and information processing.

Table 2.2. Building blocks for Implementing the Function "Choosing" of the "Coordination Method"

Communications	Building blocks
Direct	2.1. Collective simulation of various options for joint activities. Exchanging information on cost/benefit assessments for each option. Identifying the current set of options that different participants consider the best and informing everyone about these options.
Indirect	2.2. Individual simulation of various options for the participant's own activity based on assumptions formed through observations of changes in the shared environment and the states of other participants. Individual assessment of expected costs/benefits for each option and selection of an activity option that considers the expected demand for the results of their activities.
Absent	2.3. Individual assessment of costs/benefits for various options of one's own activities based on the assumption that other participants are acting under similar rules. Individual identification of the best options for their own activities that are possible within the rules applicable to the current situation.

The blocks from Table 2.2 differ in participants' abilities to find the best option for their joint activities.

Table 2.3. Building blocks for Implementing the Function "Coordinating" of the "Coordination Method"

Communications	Building blocks
Direct	3.1. Participants use direct and feedback communications to negotiate and seek compromises in determining the best option for all under current conditions based on the expected cost/benefit ratio. Instead of agreeing on the best option, participants may settle for an acceptable option, as continuing the negotiation process increases their costs and reduces expected benefits. While selecting an acceptable option, participants can simultaneously continue searching for a better option.
Indirect	3.2. Participants use indirect feedback loop, where they explore the content of their activities that will be best received by other participants through trial and error. By doing so, participants gradually move toward mutually agreed-upon content for their joint activities.
Absent	3.3. Participants act by trial and error, but without feedback on each other's actions. Only feedback loop through observation of the state of the common environment operates. Determination of the content of the activity based on common rules ensures the coordination of their activity in a degenerate form. The participation of the regulator in the coordination process is possible.

The elements from Table 2.3 differ in participants' abilities to collectively choose the best content for their joint activities based on the cost/benefit ratio.

Table 2.4. Building blocks for Implementing the Function "Responsibility" of the "Governance Method"

Communications	Building blocks
Direct	4.1. The assignment of responsibility occurs within the framework of the process of collective agreement on the content of the activity and the decision to transfer the joint activity to the implementation mode.
Indirect	4.2. Participants individually make decisions about the content and initiation of their activities, assuming the associated risks.
Absent	4.3. Participants fix their responsibility, acting on the basis of the given common rules. They individually decide to transfer the activity to the implementation mode. The lack of feedback between themselves can be compensated by the creation of a centralized regulator.

The elements from Table 2.4 differ in participants' abilities to adapt decisions to changing conditions.

Table 2.5. Building blocks for Implementing the Function "Monitoring" of the "Governance Method"

Communications	Building blocks
Direct	5.1. Monitoring of changes related to joint activities is collective in nature and is an integral part of the implementation process.
Indirect	5.2. Monitoring is individual in nature and is a natural part of the process of observing changes in the common environment, including those related to the activities of other participants. Additional monitoring from the regulator is possible.
Absent	5.3. Similar to indirect communications.

The elements from Table 2.5 differ in participants' abilities to collectively track disturbances affecting joint activities.

Table 2.6. Building blocks for Implementing the Function "Sustainability" of the "Governance Method"

Communications	Building blocks
Direct	6.1. Collective resolution of problem situations related to disturbances by participants. This is achieved by returning to negotiations and agreements, resulting in participants either eliminating disturbances (for example, by changing the composition of participants), adjusting (re-coordinating) the content of their activities, or modifying the structure of the mechanism they use for joint activities to adapt to changes.
Indirect	6.2. Participants can only address their individual disturbances. For disturbances that cannot be eliminated, participants may establish a centralized regulator to resolve emerging situations in their common interest.
Absent	6.3. Similar to indirect communications.

The elements from Table 2.6 differ in participants' abilities to collectively respond to disturbances.

Appendix 3. Example of Description of an Institution-Type Mechanism Based on the Building Blocks of an Abstract Mechanism

We illustrate the description of an institution-type mechanism using one of Ostrom's examples (Ostrom, 2005, p. 248): lobstermen in Maine. We generalize this example as fishermen fishing in a common body of water. In this case, the fishermen are forced to engage in joint activities, since they cannot exclude each other from fishing. The activity of each of them at any given moment reduces the amount of fish available to the others. This creates interdependencies between them and turns their activities into joint activities. Since, with reasonable fishing, the amount of fish can be restored over time, the fishermen are forced to regulate their joint activities in order to maintain the ability to fish for a long time. Thus, the fishermen need a mechanism with some method of coordination that will allow them to coordinate their current activities, as well as a method of governance that will ensure the sustainability of their joint activities over time.

In their joint activities, fishermen use all three modes of communication to perform the functions of coordination and governance of their joint activities.

Coordination method. In the process of catching fish, fishermen observe the amount of fish in the reservoir, which allows them to make assumptions about the content of the activities of other fishermen. That is, the "accounting" function of the coordination method is implemented based on indirect communications (building block 1.2.). Let us assume that the process of catching fish is regulated only by common rules that do not require current communications between fishermen. Then the choice of options for joint activities and their coordination (the "choosing" and "coordinating" functions of the coordination method) are implemented by fishermen strictly individually based on their assumptions that everyone acts according to common rules, as well as taking into account the information received from observations. Implementation of these functions in the absence of communications means the use of building blocks 2.3 and 3.3.

Governance method. The "responsibility" function is implemented on the basis of rules (building block 4.3.) regulating the activities of fishermen, i.e. fishermen individually assess their risks, and the regulator monitors their behavior. The "monitoring" function is implemented by fishermen through observation (building block 5.2.) of the amount of fish in the reservoir, i.e. on the basis of indirect communications. Observations provide them with information on how the common rules work or to what extent these rules are followed. The "sustainability" function, in addition to its implementation on the basis of the rules and actions of the regulator (building block 6.3.), can be implemented on the basis of direct communications (building block 6.1.). Upon receiving important information from indirect communications, i.e. observations of the amount of fish in the reservoir, fishermen can establish direct communications with each other in order to agree on adjusting the current rules, on applying sanctions, on changing the composition of participants, etc.

The core activity, i.e. catching fish, is carried out by fishermen without communication with each other. Coordination, which in this case means reasonable behavior of fishermen, is achieved by following common rules for all, and indirect and direct communications are used in the governance process to ensure the sustainability of joint activities. Thus, for the operation of the mechanism of joint activity, fishermen use a certain combination of communication modes. It is logical to assume that the place of specific modes in this combination is determined, on the one hand, by the desire of fishermen to reduce their communication costs, and on the other hand, by the desire to obtain more benefit over a certain period of time.

In this context, a natural answer to Ostrom's slightly paraphrased question: how to create a mechanism of joint activity that can be dynamic, adaptive, and effective over time? (Ostrom, 2005, p. 271) is to define an algorithm for the dynamic selection of building blocks that will provide the best possible ratio between the costs of the mechanism and the benefit from the core activity under current conditions.